

Cubic Mn₃Ge thin films stabilized through epitaxial growth as a candidate noncollinear antiferromagnet

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Supplemental Material

Thin film growth details

Mn₃Ge thin films were grown using magnetron sputtering in a BESTEC deposition system with a base pressure $< 2 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar and using a process gas (Ar 5 N) pressure of 3×10^{-3} mbar. The target to substrate distance was fixed at 200 mm and the substrates were rotated during deposition to ensure homogeneous growth. Films with various thicknesses were grown heteroepitaxially on single-crystal (111)-cut SrTiO₃ (STO) substrates with a Ru buffer layer, as follows:

STO (111) / Ru (5 or 10 nm) / Mn₃Ge (10, 30 or 40 nm) / Al (3 nm).

For the growth, we used Ru (\varnothing 51 mm), Mn (\varnothing 76 mm), Ge (\varnothing 58 mm), and Al (\varnothing 58 mm) sources in confocal geometry. Ru was deposited by applying 40 W, Mn by applying 30 W, Ge by applying 12 W, and Al by applying 20 W of DC power, respectively. The Ru underlayer was grown at 400°C. Mn₃Ge was deposited at room temperature (RT) and then annealed in-situ under ultra-high vacuum at 400°C for 10 min. The Al capping layer was grown at RT. For exchange bias experiments, we deposited 5 nm of Permalloy (Py) on top of the Mn₃Ge at RT (using a \varnothing 51 mm Ni₈₁Fe₁₉ at.% target operated at 40 W).

Crystal structure measurement methods

X-ray diffraction (XRD) and X-ray reflectivity (XRR) were measured in a Panalytical X'Pert3 MRD diffractometer, using Cu $K_{\alpha 1}$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). We recorded reciprocal space maps (RSM) using a Panalytical Empyrean system equipped with an X-ray mirror producing a parallel Cu $K_{\alpha 1}$ beam and a large area detector (Medipix, 512 \times 512 pixels). Conventional transmission electron microscopy (TEM), high-resolution TEM (HRTEM) and scanning TEM (STEM) were imaged in a FEI Titan 80-300 microscope. For STEM imaging, we applied the high-angle annular dark-field technique (HAADF-STEM), whilst using a built-in energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDXS) detector for element mapping. Cross-section lamella were prepared by focused ion beam milling. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) topographic maps were collected in non-contact mode using a MFP-3D Origin+ microscope from Oxford Instruments Asylum Research.

Reciprocal space map in perpendicular crystal plane

Figure S1. Reciprocal space maps measured with (a) the $[11\bar{2}]$ and $[111]$ directions (as shown in Figure 1), and (b) the $[1\bar{1}0]$ and $[111]$ directions, of the substrate as the x- and y-axis, respectively. The symbols denote the nominal positions of Bragg peaks from the different layers and of the different candidate crystal structures of Mn_3Ge . The same symbols are used when displaying the pole figures, Figure S2.

Pole figure X-ray diffraction measurements

To further confirm the cubic phase, we measured XRD pole figures using a Panalytical Empyrean system in combination with a point detector at the corresponding azimuthal angles sensitive to different sets of Bragg reflections, shown in Figure S2. These measured data are overlaid with the expected peak positions of: *c*- Mn_3Ge (220) in Figure S2a; SrTiO_3 (310) and Ru (103) in Figure S2b; SrTiO_3 (222), Ru (201) and *c*- Mn_3Ge (113) in Figure S2c; and SrTiO_3 (233), Ru (114) and *c*- Mn_3Ge (024) in Figure S2d.

Again, our measured crystal structure is only consistent with the cubic phase. In this case, *c*- Mn_3Ge peaks should have three-fold symmetry. However, this is doubled to a six-fold symmetry. The additional Bragg peaks confirm surface normal twinned domains within the *c*- Mn_3Ge layer, as previously identified through TEM analysis.

Figure S2. Pole figure measurements of a STO (111) / Ru (5nm) / Mn₃Ge (40 nm) sample at various azimuthal angles (a-d). Due to a finite angular resolution of the detector, reflections from different lattice planes of SrTiO₃, Ru and Mn₃Ge sometimes show up in the same measurement. The symbols denote the nominal positions of Bragg peaks from the different layers and of the different candidate crystal structures of Mn₃Ge (and are the same as those used in Figure S1).

Epitaxial crystal structure of exchange bias bilayers

Figure S3 shows the 2θ - θ XRD pattern of a *c*-Mn₃Ge (40 nm) / Py (5 nm) bilayer. We observe weak (111) reflections from the Py layer, indicating that a partial (111) texture is seeded into the Py by the Mn₃Ge film. This suggests a sharp, smooth interface between the two layers, which will limit any contribution of roughness to exchange bias and potentially provide a transparent interface for spin current propagation from the *c*-Mn₃Ge to Py films.

Figure S3. X-ray diffraction pattern of a *c*-Mn₃Ge (40 nm) / Py (5 nm) bilayer.

Specifics of computational methods

The structural minimization of the hexagonal and cubic lattices was carried out using the VASP density functional theory package, within the generalized gradient approximation parameterization [1]. For both structures, we use a k-point grid of 8×8×8. For the hexagonal structure, we use the experimental lattice constants $c / a = 0.807$. For the cubic structure, we note that, because of the shallow minimum of the energy per unit cell volume, the experimentally observed small rhombohedral distortion is not considered in further calculations.

The subsequent calculation of the exchange parameters for the cubic structure was performed in the full-potential linearized augmented plane wave package of the FLEUR code [2], using the experimental lattice constant. Here, we use a k -point grid of $16 \times 16 \times 16$ and a q -point grid of $8 \times 8 \times 8$, considering 100 nearest-neighbor shells. We derive the Wannier interpolated Hamiltonian using the projected d -orbitals of Mn and the s, p -orbitals of Ge. These are calculated within the unit cell using the generalized Bloch theorem applied to spin spirals in combination with the Andersen force theorem [3, 4]. We obtain the exchange interactions as a Fourier transform, $J_{ij}(\mathbf{R}) = \frac{1}{V_{BZ}} \int_{V_{BZ}} J_{ij}(\mathbf{q}) e^{-i\mathbf{q} \cdot (\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{R})} d^3 \mathbf{q}$, in a mapping to a Heisenberg Hamiltonian [5, 6]. We checked the existence of Weyl points between band n and band $n+1$, where n is the electron number in the unit cell, with the bandgap converging to 10^{-6} eV.

Exchange bias measurement protocol and training effect in a c-Mn₃Ge (40 nm) / Py (5 nm) bilayer

Exchange bias was measured using three different approaches: (i) Cooling from 400 K in a 1-T in-plane (IP) magnetic field to progressively decreasing temperatures, then measuring hysteresis loops to extract exchange bias field ($\mu_0 H_{EB}$) and coercive field ($\mu_0 H_c$). At base temperature, ten field cycles were recorded and changes in the hysteresis loop observed. The data in Figures S4 and S5 were measured using this protocol. (ii) Demagnetizing at 350 K, then cooling in a 1-T IP magnetic field to 5 K (T_{base}). At T_{base} , five field cycles were recorded, with $\mu_0 H_{EB}$ and $\mu_0 H_c$ extracted. The sample was then warmed to progressively higher temperatures (T_{meas}), with hysteresis loops measured at each temperature. This protocol yields the maximum exchange bias that can be achieved on field cooling and was used to measure the data shown in Figure 4a. (iii) Demagnetizing at 350 K, then cooling in zero field to progressively decreasing temperatures (T_{start}), then turning on a 1-T IP magnetic field and cooling further to 5 K. At T_{base} , a hysteresis loop was then measured, with $\mu_0 H_{EB}$ and $\mu_0 H_c$ extracted for each T_{start} . This protocol allows the robust determination of blocking temperature (T_B), because exchange bias will only arise if $T_{start} > T_B$, and is therefore used to measure the data in Figure 4b.

Figure S4. Exchange bias training effect in a c-Mn₃Ge (40 nm) / Py (5 nm) bilayer showing the variation of exchange bias and coercive fields at 5 K after consecutive training-field cycles, after cooling from 400 K in a 1-T magnetic field applied along the $[1\bar{1}0]$ direction.

Multiple hysteresis loops are recorded in order to evaluate the robustness of the exchange bias to the so-called training effect, a phenomenon whereby the exchange bias may decrease after repeated external field cycles. Figure S4 presents the variation of the exchange bias and coercive fields with consecutive training-field cycles following 1-T IP field cooling from 400 K to 5 K. After the third applied field cycle, we obtain consistent values of $\mu_0 H_{EB} \approx 8$ mT. By this point, any weakly pinned uncompensated moments at the interface have relaxed, and the resulting exchange bias is stabilized only by interfacial Mn moments which are strongly coupled to the bulk AF order.

Figure S5. Exchange bias in a $c\text{-Mn}_3\text{Ge}$ (10 nm) / Py (5 nm) bilayer. μ_0H_{EB} and μ_0H_c measured at different temperatures after cooling from 400 K in a 1-T magnetic field applied along (a) the $[\bar{1}\bar{1}2]$ direction and (b) the $[1\bar{1}0]$ direction of the film. (c) Exchange bias training effect showing the variation of μ_0H_{EB} and μ_0H_c after consecutive external magnetic field cycles at 5 K, following cooling from 400 K in a 1-T magnetic field applied along the $[1\bar{1}0]$ direction. (d) Normalized magnetization hysteresis loops of the as-deposited bilayer at 300 K, and at 10 K after ZFC and $\pm 1\text{-T}$ IP FC.

Exchange bias in a $c\text{-Mn}_3\text{Ge}$ (10 nm) / Py (5 nm) bilayer

Figure S5 depicts the exchange bias of a $c\text{-Mn}_3\text{Ge}$ (10 nm) / Py (5 nm) bilayer. Figures S5a and b show the temperature dependence of μ_0H_{EB} and μ_0H_c along two different crystallographic directions. In both cases, the rapid increase of μ_0H_{EB} and μ_0H_c below 30 K indicates the onset of exchange anisotropy in the heterostructure. This allows us to place the blocking temperature of the 10 nm $c\text{-Mn}_3\text{Ge}$ film in this

range. Blocking temperature is similar to that of the 40-nm-thick film, as expected for epitaxially grown films where crystallite grain size (and therefore antiferromagnetic domain pinning sites) are not dominated by finite size effects.

The exchange bias training effect for this 10-nm-thick film is presented in Figure S5c. After the second applied field cycle, the Mn spins relax and we obtain consistent values of $\mu_0 H_{EB} \approx 9.5$ mT and $\mu_0 H_c \approx 42.5$ mT. Figure S5d shows the normalized magnetization hysteresis loops of the as-deposited bilayer at 300 K, and at 10 K after zero field cooling (ZFC) and ± 1 -T IP field cooling (FC) respectively. In the as-deposited state, no shift or broadening of the loop is observed. The ZFC loop shows broadening but no shift. The FC loops shift along the applied field axis and show an increased coercivity, indicating the onset of exchange bias at low temperatures.

Magnetic and transport property measurement techniques

High temperature longitudinal resistivity was measured in an unpatterned film using inverting direct current and electrical contacts made by four stainless steel electrode tips, with the film placed in a glass tube under Ar gas. Field-dependent and low-temperature transport was performed in Hall bar devices, patterned using a combination of electron-beam lithography and Ar ion etching, set up in a four-terminal geometry using Al wire bonded contacts. These were measured in a Quantum Design PPMS cryostat, using either a DC current source (Keithley 6221) and nanovoltmeter (Keithley 2182A) or a low-frequency alternating excitation current combined with lock-in amplifier detection (Quantum Design ETO option).

Figure S6. Longitudinal transport measured at zero magnetic field with a 100 μ A current flowing along the $[\bar{1}\bar{1}2]$ direction for a 5 nm Ru reference sample, a Ru (5 nm) / *c*-Mn₃Ge (40 nm) multilayer, and as calculated for the 40 nm *c*-Mn₃Ge layer. (a) Device resistance either measured or extracted using parallel resistors model. (b) Material resistivity calculated from the geometry of Hall bar devices.

Parallel resistors model for calculating resistivity

Figure S6a plots the longitudinal resistance (R_{xx}) measured at zero magnetic field for a 5 nm Ru reference sample and a Ru (5 nm) / *c*-Mn₃Ge (40 nm) multilayer. By comparing the resistances, we observe that less than half of the current flows in the Ru underlayer at room temperature. To remove this current shunt, we subtract the Ru contribution using a parallel resistors model. The resulting resistance of the 40 nm *c*-Mn₃Ge film is also plotted in Figure S6a.

Low-temperature longitudinal transport measurements

We accurately quantify the longitudinal resistivity (ρ_{xx}) of *c*-Mn₃Ge at room temperature and below. To achieve this, we patterned the films into Hall bar devices, yielding a well-defined geometry in which measured R_{xx} could be converted to material ρ_{xx} . To account for current shunting through the underlayer, we subtracted the background transport signals measured from a 5 nm Ru reference sample, using a parallel resistor

model. Figure S6b shows the temperature-dependent longitudinal resistivity resulting from such calculations. We observe metallic behavior for *c*-Mn₃Ge.

Supplementary references

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